

THEORETICAL AND METHODOLOGICAL FOUNDATIONS OF TOURIST BUSINESS MANAGEMENT BASED ON PUBLIC-PRIVATE PARTNERSHIP

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Abstract. *This article provides scientific opinions on the effective use of modern innovative means of public-private partnership mechanisms to increase the tourism potential of the country's regions, transform tourism into a strategic industry, increase tourism potential through the formation of a regional tourism cluster and improve the management of the tourism sector.*

Key words: *public-private partnership, modern innovation, economic growth at the micro, meso, macro level, concession relations, production.*

It is known that the PPP mechanism is designed not only to promote economic growth of the country's regions at the micro, but also at the meso and macro levels, ensure stable and balanced development, form, protect and develop the social sphere. -economic infrastructure, increasing the volume and quality of public services, increasing the level of network use, becomes an important area for optimal use of existing opportunities in attracting foreign investors.

In the implementation of socio-economic policy in the region, PPP is of particular importance, and this innovative mechanism is an important factor in the development and promotion of innovation in the regional economic system. This, in turn, justifies the fact that PPP is a real mechanism that can be used in implementing the strategy of transition from the important state trinity of the region of the Republic of Uzbekistan to an innovative path of development.

Purpose of the study: The purpose of the research carried out when writing this article is to analyze the management of tourism businesses based on public-private partnerships..

Research methohody: PPP is a distinctive feature of public entrepreneurship and also has regional innovative value. The PPP initiative, which is a unique direction for business development, is as follows.

Such a partnership:

- Satisfies the need for a public mailbox by using or owning a private mailbox.;
- Working together with the state CAT, the national CAT supports many of the functions and powers of the state.;
- This is due to the connection of two or more transparent sides from the surface..

Participants in the PPP mechanism are local and state governments, public and non-profit organizations (for example, local communities, service clubs, social service organizations or interest groups). There will be many opportunities for the partners in this partnership.

Public-private partnership models.

Model name	Model features
Operational model	the private partner undertakes to finance the project. The object is managed. Local government determines the purpose of the project and the rules for operating the facility.

concession model	State concession to public companies on a selection basis (e.g. pipeline maintenance, utilities). This scenario is widely used in the context of experiential culture and communication.
Leasing model (real estate rental and long-term rental)	This model is used not only in the field of development, but also in the construction of social facilities, such as schools, clubs, cinemas, etc. An example of this is the lease agreement for the construction and operation of the cultural center "Gackteig" in Munich, according to which the company has the right to purchase the facility after signing the agreement.
Contract model	The responsibility for solving management tasks, such as cost reduction tasks, is assumed by the private partner. In turn, the bonus is paid at the expense of the saved fund.
Model "Build, control, transfer"	For example, under the “build, manage, transfer” model - 933 million in the city of Izmir, Turkey. 70% of the funds will be financed by 2 local companies, 15% by the city, and the remaining 15% by Japanese companies. In 15 years the facility will be transferred to the city
Land management model	This model is a method of cooperative development of individual regions, cities or districts, in which various sources of financing are attracted for the restoration and preservation of urban areas or objects of historical and cultural heritage, implemented in many cities.
Business incubators	By organizing technology centers, it ensures that innovative ideas are brought to the stage of sale, that is, commercialization, through the venture capital firms that are their creators.
Joint ventures	In Uzbekistan, joint shelters began to spread widely in the 90s of the last century.

Modern forms of PPP are characterized by more complex contractual agreements reflecting different levels of use, disposal, management and other ownership relationships.

This is manifested in the following various forms of partnership in foreign practice:

- design (Design & Construct, D&C);
- use and sale on lease terms (Sale & Leaseback, S&L);
- quick management and correct storage (Operate & Maintain, O&M);
- operational management, support and strategic management (Operate, Maintain & Manage, O&M&M);
- construction, operational management, transfer to the state (Build, Operate, Transfer, VOT);
- leasing, renewal, management, transfer (Lease, Renovate, Operate, Transfer, LROT);
- design, strategic management, financing (Design, Build, Finance, Operate, DBFO);
- design, construction, financing, operational management, strategic management (Design, Build, Finance, Operate, Manage, DBFOM).

Conclusions and Recommendations

The study of the above-mentioned forms of PPP, their effectiveness and features is an urgent task, and given the characteristics of Uzbekistan and its regions, it can be actively used at the local level and in the economy.

According to research, in order to increase the tourism potential of the region, it is advisable to use the PPP contract model, that is, to sell tourism services directly to travel agency firms or textile companies and individuals.

Because, according to the analysis carried out during the study, direct communication occupies a special place in the sale of household goods. If a certain advertisement increases the attractiveness of the product and the travel agency, then it stimulates the consumer's interest and ensures a positive perception of the information.

In Japan, selling goods or services through direct communication solves the following problems:

- establishing direct relationships with potential consumers who are interested in purchasing a product or service;
- Establishment and development of long-term stable relationships with regular consumers and clients;
- determine consumer needs for your product or service;
- providing consumers with information and consulting services in the process of making decisions about purchasing household goods;
- stimulate consumer purchases taking into account their religion, nationality, preferences, beliefs, customs and national traditions when selling household goods and consumer choice;
- adapting their appearance, packaging, labeling, service systems and models to consumer needs when monitoring consumer behavior of household goods;
- searching for effective methods of working with consumers and selling products;
- formation and maintenance of the general image of the country's tourism business, private tourism products and travel companies.

A distinctive feature of the effectiveness of direct sales of goods or services is the need to respond to the incentives of travel agents to purchase goods for the client, and to increase the level of responsibility for their choice.

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